

Spatial Resolution in Quantum Tunneling and Time to Tunnel

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There is interest in the literature about the time a quantum particle spends in the tunneling region in a potential (1),(2). Here, we argue that quantum mechanics, at least for a free particle and a bound particle in $V(x)$, seems to be a combination of classical mechanical average energy conservation and time and spatial resolution. In other words, this new spatial \hbar/p and temporal \hbar/E resolutions (for a free particle with generalizations for a bound) set quantum mechanics apart from classical mechanics.

If one considers a square well potential then classically a particle bounces back and forth in the region of the well. In quantum mechanics, we argue that the well is really an average $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$, nevertheless this average is important because in the high energy level limit, spatial and temporal resolutions are very high and the average becomes the reality. Furthermore, inside the well, one has $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n$ for any energy level and this is identical to the classical mechanical result. The catch is that there is a $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which exhibits crests and troughs within the well, i.e. spatial resolution. This average spatial resolution is important because it indicates the resolution with which the length of $V(x)$ is seen. There is also a temporal resolution \hbar/E . Thus, there is a given length in a bound problem, namely that between classical turning points together with a spatial and temporal resolution which suggest that even though on average one has the classical energy conservation condition, one may only see it with x and t resolutions. Nevertheless, the equation $L = \hbar/p$ within the well seems to make sense given the resolutions.

Outside the square well, matters are different. There is no fixed length, rather distances tend to infinite and so $W(x)$ must tend to zero if $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents spatial probability. In the literature,, however, the region under $W^*(x)W(x)$, where this density is substantial, is sometimes considered to be the tunneling region and there is an attempt to attach a time interval to it, i.e. the amount of time spent tunneling based on $-\int dx \hbar / |p(x)|$ based on extending ideas within the well to the complex plane.

We suggest that there is a possible problem with this because there is limited spatial resolution in this region. In particular, $W(x)$ defines the region and the spatial resolution at the same time and one cannot see x point samples within this region, similar to a ground state. The ground state, however, has zeros on both sides whereas the tunneling $W(x)$ only decreases on one side so one does not really have an x endpoint at the square well edge. Thus, it seems that one does not have x resolution to define the tunneling region. Thus, we suggest it is difficult to use an equation based on distance = \hbar/p if one cannot resolve x points within this region. One cannot sense the full tunneling region with a resolution which matches the region.

The average kinetic energy is negative suggesting an imaginary average momentum, yet the components $\exp(ipx)$ of $W(x)$ in this region represent a positive $p^2/2m$ and a real momentum. Thus, individual free component spatial resolution is not lost nor is overall time resolution $\exp(-iEt)$ where $E < 0$. Only average spatial resolution is lost suggesting that from a quantum mechanical viewpoint one cannot really resolve space in this region. If that is the case, it does not seem to make sense to consider the time spent in the tunneling region, at least in terms of an average $-\int dx \hbar / |p(x)|$ associated with $W^*(x)W(x)$.

Tunneling Time

In (1), a semiclassical approach is described (along with others) in the tunneling region outside of a square well, i.e.

$$p(x) = \sqrt{2m(E-V(x))} \quad ((1))$$

Momentum is negative in the tunneling region (because KE is negative) and so one has the integral:

$$\text{Time} = \int dx \quad m/p(x) \quad ((2)) \text{ in the complex plane.}$$

$$(1) \text{ considers the result } \text{time} = -i \int_{x^-}^{x^+} m dy / |p| \quad ((3))$$

and notes that some people in the literature consider this to be the time spent in the tunneling region. (1), however, does not necessarily endorse this result and presents arguments using added Gaussian bursts to a perturbation potential to show that the particle seems to spend almost zero time in the tunneling region.

The Issue of Resolution

We argue that if one uses an equation such as $x = vt$, which is the source of ((2)) in the first place, then one must be able to resolve space and time, i.e. in the tunneling region. For a nonrelativistic free particle, $\exp(ipx)\exp(-iEt)$ shows that the spatial resolution is \hbar/p and temporal \hbar/E . \hbar/p has the consequence of leading to 2-slit interference and governing the probabilities to reflect/refract in one dimensional reflection/refraction.

In the case of a square well potential, the region within the potential is the usual classical bound region, i.e. the region between the classical turning points. This length is imposed by the potential, but for motion to make sense within this region, one must show, it seems, that one has spatial and temporal resolution higher than the length L (between turning points) and the associated classical time. From the solution of the time independent Schrodinger equation, one has $C_1 \sin(pave x/\hbar) + C_2 \cos(pavex/\hbar)$ for $x=0$ to $x=L$. This sinusoid shows the x resolution and it is clearly higher than L or equal to L in the ground state.

For temporal resolution, we consider the case of an infinite well potential as an estimate:

$$L = \hbar v_e / m T \quad \text{where } pav_e = n \cdot 3.14 / L \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{The temporal resolution follows from } \exp(-iEt) \text{ where } E = \frac{\hbar^2 n^2 \cdot 3.14^2}{2mL^2} \quad ((5))$$

Thus, in the case of the infinite well $T/\text{quantum} < 1$ ((6)) i.e., one can resolve motion in x and t in L .

For a finite well, there is an oscillatory wavefunction $W(x)$ within the well and so there is guaranteed spatial resolution in this region. For the temporal case, (3) shows an example with:

$$E = 2 \hbar^2 v_1 v_2 / (mL) \quad \text{with } v_1 = 1.28 \quad v_2 = 2.54 \quad \text{and } v_3 = 3.73$$

where $k = \sqrt{2mE}/\hbar$ Thus: $L = \hbar k/m T$

$$T/t_{\text{quantum}} = (Lm/\sqrt{2mE}) \quad E = Lm/(\sqrt{2m}) \sqrt{2v_1 v_2 / mL} = \sqrt{v_1 v_2} > 1$$

Thus, there is still both temporal and spatial resolution within the square well potential region.

In this same region, $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ where each free particle has kinetic energy $pp/2m$ and real momentum p .

The issue seems to be what happens outside the well. There, $\exp(-iEt)$ still holds, but $E < 0$. $\hbar/|E|$ is the temporal resolution, but average kinetic energy is negative leading to a purely imaginary average momentum. One has $W(x) = \exp(-p_{\text{ave}} x)$ where p_{ave} is a real positive number for $x > 0$. The problem, we argue, is that this wavefunction does not show any spatial resolution even though it is real. We argue that an important idea of the spatial $W(x)$ is to show resolution. We note that $\exp(-p_{\text{ave}} x)$ is still composed of $\exp(ipx)$ s which represent a real positive kinetic energy of $pp/2m$ and a momentum of p .

We ask: What does $W(x)$ show outside of the classical turning points? Given that $W^*(x)W(x)$ is spatial density, it shows this, but we argue that since there is no distinct spatial resolution, $W(x)$ shows the interaction with $V(x) = \sum \text{over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$ in this region and there is no average spatial resolution which emerges so quantum mechanically one cannot argue that this region is spatially seen, at least in terms of an average. It is almost like the case of a ground state. As a result, we suggest that using $L = p/m t$ makes sense in the $V(x)$ classical turning points region, and we used this above, but one cannot use such an equation in the tunneling region. $W(x)$ outside the edge of the square well drops as $\exp(-|p_{\text{ave}}|x)$, but for resolution one wishes to have two 0 points such that the resolution length lies in between, it seems. One does not have this for the tunneling region.

The time resolution for the square well follows from distance of peak outside well = $(|p_{\text{ave}}|/m) T$ with $|E| = |p_{\text{ave}}|^2/2m$. Then

$$T/t_{\text{quantum}} = E \text{ Distance } m/ p_{\text{ave}} = p_{\text{ave}}/2 D \quad \text{where } 0 \text{ approx} = \exp(-p_{\text{ave}} D).$$

For $D = 3/p_{\text{ave}}$ one has $T/t_{\text{quantum}} = 1.5$ and so one has acceptable time resolution, but the spatial resolution is approx $D = 3/p_{\text{ave}}$ and the tunneling occurs mostly within D and so spatial resolution is not very good, it seems.

Thus, we would caution the use of ((3)) as the time spent in the tunneling region. This is similar to the case of a ground state where the quantum resolution does not really see the whole length range within the classical turning points. The ground state, however, represents the

lowest energy state. One might expect a higher energy state would approximate motion between classical turning points with better resolution.

Conclusion

We suggest that quantum mechanics provides spatial and temporal resolutions and that these are key in determining what is seen or not, as in the 2-slit interference case. We suggest that temporal and spatial resolutions indicate whether $L = \hbar v_e / m T$ makes sense for a constant v_e in a square well with L being the width of the well. If $\hbar v_e / m T$ and $\hbar v_e / |E|$ are not smaller than L and the $T = L / v_e$, then one cannot sense motion very well in this region. We argue, however, that there is enough resolution to sense motion and this resolution becomes sharper with higher energy.

We then argue that in the tunneling region, outside the classical turning points, one still has $\hbar v_e / |E|$ for temporal resolution, but no average spatial resolution because $W(x) = C \exp(-\kappa x)$ for $x > 0$ (and a similar expression for $x < 0$). In other words the spatial resolution represents the tunneling region, like in a ground state except that a ground state has two zero points, while $W(x)$ outside the square well goes as $\exp(-\kappa |x|)$ and so there is only one approximate 0 point. One is unable to sample various x points (or even the beginning and end point) throughout this region to justify distance = $\hbar v_e / m T$.

We suggest that $W^*(x)W(x)$ equals the spatial probability in this region and also shows how the particle interacts with $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. We note that $\exp(-\kappa x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ where each $\exp(ipx)$ represents an real p and a positive $p^2/2m$, but that $(i\kappa v_e)(i\kappa v_e)/2m$ represents a negative average kinetic energy and shows the interaction with the potential in this region due to the $V_k \exp(ikx)$ pieces. With not enough spatial resolution, we argue that one cannot resolve the particle presence in the tunneling spatial region and so one cannot use any distance = $p/m t$ equations in this region and so we would caution against using ((3)) to represent time to tunnel.

References

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